

A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH TO A DIGITAL TWIN BASED ON ASSET ADMINISTRATION SHELLS FOR A PROCESS CHAIN OF AUTOMATED TAPE LAYING AND THERMOFORMING FOR STRUCTURAL AEROSPACE COMPONENT MANUFACTURING

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Keywords: Digital Twin, Asset Administration Shell, Life Cycle Assessment, Automated Tape Laying, Thermoforming

ABSTRACT

In the aviation sector, highest demands are placed on the mechanical properties, quality and traceability of all components. Complex manufacturing processes such as Automated Tape Laying (ATL) and subsequent thermoforming imply comprehensive quality inspections to meet strict air transport safety regulations. Utilizing these processes to produce parts fulfilling the harsh requirements needs exact process control and knowledge about every aspect of the process chain. Each processing step generates huge amounts of machine not currently stored in a common, centralized form. A digital twin describing the products along the chain is created to store and transmit this data in a standardized structure and common format as a necessary requirement for overarching process control and life cycle analysis (LCA). This is achieved by means of the Asset Administration Shell (AAS), a standardized approach to implement vendor-independent digital twins and to provide an interoperable meta-model to represent relevant information. Instances of the AAS contain data for all process steps, wherein several sub-models contain general data in standardized models in combination with a self-defined model leveraging classical laminate theory (CLT). Standardized models allow taking advantage of standards beyond the boundaries of composite specific process data, such as the Product Carbon Footprint (PCF) used in the calculation of the LCA. The composite specific model retains the relevant data for composites. Due to the integration in the AAS, all data is transformed into a common shape, ensuring all data to be useable. This integration of information can be shared across processes, applications and industries. The models along the process chain are presented in this contribution, providing subject for discussion.

1 MOTIVATION

In the aviation sector, highest demands are placed on all mechanical properties, quality and traceability of all components to meet strict air transport safety regulations. As a result of this, rigorous inventory recording and tracking for all used materials, components and assemblies up to final products is mandatory. A current challenge therefore is to digitalize the documentation of these processes and test results whilst adhering to existing standards and established concepts. In addition to safety, social and governance reasons, documentation of environmental impacts has become an additional requirement. In order to precisely compute the ecological footprint of the manufacturing of structural aerospace components, processes have become the focus of data collection. At the same time, this data is an valuable asset for controlling and predicting the quality of components along the whole processing chain.

2 INTRODUCTION

To support the digitalization of aerospace manufacturing and enable precise process control, as well as continuous Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), the processes of Automated Tape Laying (ATL) and Thermoforming (TF) were digitalized. This includes the comprehensive assessment of process parameters and results, which are essential for reducing environmental impact. The rejection of defective components significantly increases the overall environmental footprint of accepted parts, making quality improvement a critical objective. To represent realistic starting points in the industry, existing software systems were not replaced, but instead new capabilities were to be added.

The solution created in the scope of this work is thus designed with a non-monolithic architecture to ensure seamless integration with existing enterprise environments. Unlike tightly coupled solutions, this approach avoids interference with established Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES), and Supply Chain Management (SCM) systems, which already manage parts of the information necessary to describe the digital twin. Instead of replacing or altering internal digital twin implementations, these are extended through the Asset Administration Shell (AAS), as defined by the Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA), which functions as a standardized and shareable external representation. It is utilized, because it is an industry-neutral standard with broad applicability, and has strong potential for long-term market relevance. An additional benefit as depicted in Figure 1 is the improved control over shared and published data. The external layer created by the AAS (blue) enables interoperability while maintaining strict data sovereignty. Confidential and internal company data remain fully contained within the organization's secure network (grey). The AAS merely references selected data elements that are explicitly defined for external use through control of a firewall-layer (yellow), ensuring that sensitive information is neither exposed nor transferred. Only access-controlled links to designated non-sensitive attributes are instantiated, preserving the integrity and independence of internal systems. The physical manufacturing layer (orange) and the internal layer communicate as before without experiencing change. As a result, the solution supports a high degree of system independence and facilitates structured external collaboration without compromising internal security or operational workflows.

Figure 1: Representation of relationships between modelling layers in the internal and external solution as well as the physically accessible field level where data is produced and consumed for manufacturing

3 STATE OF THE ART

3.1 Life Cycle Assessment for Composite Manufacturing

One central driving aspect of the creation of the process-focused digitalization across industry is LCA, although it is closely followed by the aspect of process control. Accordingly, it is the most important subject meeting requirements and assess achievable results by the creation of the digital twin as in the European unions (EU) Battery Passport [1]. As it will likely become mandatory for a growing number of products, it is already a focus in many digitalization attempts and will remain so here.

LCA is an environmental evaluation tool for determining or predicting the potential effects associated with a product or a process that includes its entire life cycle. The conduction of LCA is standardized in DIN EN ISO 14040 (Principles and Framework) and DIN EN ISO 14044 (Requirements and Guidelines). As an iterative approach, its four phases, namely *Goal and Scope Definition*, *Life Cycle Inventory*, *Life Cycle Impact Assessment*, and *Interpretation* are interrelated and refined throughout the study. It is also a holistic approach, considering the entire life cycle of a product following a cradle-to-grave perspective, from raw material extraction to disposal and end-of-life treatment. An LCA study typically considers multiple impact categories (e.g. *Climate Change*, *Ozone Depletion*, *Human Toxicity*), whereas a Product Carbon Footprint (PCF) only assesses the climate change impact of greenhouse gas emissions. The choice of the evaluated impact categories must be documented during the *Goal and Scope Definition* phase. Incorporating multiple impact categories prevents burden shifting between environmental issues and represents a fundamental aspect of the holistic approach. During the *Life Cycle Inventory* (LCI) phase, all input and output flows relating to the unit processes of the product system under investigation are compiled and quantified. These include raw materials, energy, products (such as services, software or hardware), elementary flows (those extracted from or released into the environment) and waste. In the *Life Cycle Impact Assessment* (LCIA) phase, the results from the LCI are assigned to the different impact categories to which they contribute. A single flow can contribute to multiple impact categories.

LCA can be used as a predictive tool to estimate environmental impact under different scenarios. FERRARI ET AL. [2] applied the methodology to evaluate the environmental impacts of various production scenarios involving raw materials from different suppliers in the ceramic tile manufacturing process. In field of composites materials, raw materials account for a significant share of the environmental impact, particularly the production of carbon fibers. According to BENITEZ ET AL. [3], the impact of carbon fiber production on climate change under the conditions of the study (2019) was estimated at 69.12 kg CO₂-eq./kg, while PRENZEL ET AL. [4] reports a range from 13 to 34.1 kg CO₂-eq./kg. The wide range of results can be explained by various factors influencing the impact on climate change during carbon fiber production, such as the type of precursor used, the energy source for precursor and fiber production, the conversion rate from precursor to carbon fiber, and the geographical location of the plant [4,5]. The method applied by the LCA practitioner can additionally influence the results, for example through the choice of system boundaries, functional units or allocations [5]. Using LCA as a predictive tool enables the optimization of composite material manufacturing processes, with the dual objective of improving efficiency and minimizing environmental impacts. The rejection rate during the manufacturing process considerably influences the final LCA results, due to the high environmental cost of carbon fibers. According to LCA methodology, all material flows intended for disposal without recovery are categorized as waste flows in the LCI phase. Despite not contributing to the final product, their associated environmental burdens are included in the overall assessment.

In the context of this study, the environmental impact of the Automated Tape Laying (ATL) and thermoforming process chain is assessed with a focus on the *Climate Change* impact category. The emphasis is placed on the digitalization of manufacturing processes following a gate-to-gate approach. Transportation, use and retail, as well as end-of-life phases are out of the scope of this study. The impacts of raw materials are considered at the process level by monitoring the rejection rate, with the aim of optimizing each process step of the production chain and minimizing its environmental impact.

3.2 Digital Twins for Composite Manufacturing Processes

Whilst there have been several proposals for the definition of the term *Digital Twin*, the concept mostly is used to describe few commonalities. A digital twin is in general a virtual representation of an object or system designed not only to represent, but to reflect a physical object accurately. It spans the physical object life cycle, updates in real time from corresponding data and provides insight into its condition and behavior.

Digital twins are mostly a concept for information provision and evaluation, which utilizes the communication capability of product systems and aggregates data from the entire product life cycle. In this way, they are a perfect fit for the continuous LCA alongside the process chain, providing current values in real time, but also quality centered process monitoring since state variables can be monitored in a central location in real time for every process and product.

Whilst the general concept of digital twins is easy to describe, fine details can make lots of differences especially considering the environment and planned usage as well as the framework and implementation. Whilst environment and usage are defined by the objective undertaken in this work, the framework to be used is subject of discussion and the implementation will be based around this decision. GIL ET AL. [6] provide a comparison and overview over different open-source digital twin frameworks, underlining the importance of AAS-based implementation as standardized solutions, whilst also pointing out the incompleteness of the frameworks.

In order to enable digital product representations that support LCA, interoperable and standardized information models are essential. The AAS plays a key role in realizing this requirement within the Industry 4.0 framework. It provides a digital representation of any physical or virtual asset, such as a machine, sensor or workpiece using an unified metamodel that allows structured data exchange across system boundaries [7].

The AAS consists of modular submodels, which cover a wide range of domains such as production planning, material properties, process capabilities, and more [8]. These submodels follow standardized structures, making data from heterogeneous systems interoperable. This makes the AAS a foundational technology for enabling cross-organizational collaboration and dynamic value chains, which are essential in modern, sustainable manufacturing scenarios [9–11].

AAS-based submodels are being successively standardized by the IDTA to ensure compatibility across industries and applications. However, in specific domains such as composite material products, standardized submodels for relevant data like material composition are not yet available. Importantly, the AAS framework supports the development of custom submodels, allowing domain-specific extensions to be added in a structured and interoperable manner [12]. This extensibility enables companies to integrate domain specific information models, still maintaining compatibility with the broader Industry 4.0 ecosystem.

3.3 The Process Chain

Since the subject of LCA and digital twins is closely related to future manufacturing of aerospace composite components, the process modelled in this work should reflect those attributes as well. Due to their specific benefits, a growing percentage of thermoplastic composites in aerospace applications can be observed in future aircrafts, used mainly in fuselage components. While many manufacturing processes are slow and costly, the thermoforming process has made it into regular production. This is due to high-rate capability, allowing the production of large panels, doors and frames [13].

Stamp forming of thermoplastic composite laminates is typically a two-step process: Fully impregnated laminates are heated in an oven to melt the matrix and to allow deformation and shearing of the laminate to fit to the later 3D-geometry. From the oven it is transferred quickly into a press, where it is stamp formed in a tool and cooled below melting point in a single step, producing the finished part within seconds. Due to the near-net-shape design of the laminate, only little machining of the part is needed, if the design of the component is optimized for thermoforming. [14, 15]

Both steps of the process – heating and thermoforming - are performed within the same equipment, a forming press with an integrated infrared oven (LZK-Uk-2600-SO, Langzauner GmbH Austria). Being equipped with a multitude of sensors, it is capable of tracking and recording all relevant processing parameters, such as pressures, positions and other states of the machine during the process. Additionally,

temperatures are monitored within the integrated infrared oven, individually controlling the 234 radiators for reproducible process conditions. Nonetheless, it also integrates a thermal camera to document temperature distribution during transfer from oven into the press during the short transfer time of approximately a second. All data is collected within an integrated process data logging system (LZ perfectDATA, Langzauner GmbH, Austria) and distributed over Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT).

To reduce the high cost and high waste of consolidated laminates, near-net-shape preforms can be manufactured in ATL with Unidirectional Reinforced Thermoplastic Tapes (UD-Tapes). A preform is a pre-consolidated laminate that is fully consolidated in the press. ATL allows load-path optimized tape placement and is suitable for high rate production of nearly flat structures such as skins and panels [16–18]. These flat tape preforms can be used as semi-finished parts for the subsequent stamp forming of three-dimensional components. Since there is a higher potential for process induced errors while placing individual tapes, there is a high demand for quality control [19,20].

The ATL machine used (F2-Compositor, ASH Automation Steeg & Hoffmeyer GmbH, Germany) is optimized for high speed deposition (up to 4 m/s) and can process UD-Tapes based on engineering as well as high performance thermoplastic polymers. To create adhesion of the individual layers, the polymer in the tape surface is molten by a hot gas torch, followed by rapid cooling under consolidation force provided by a consolidation roller. During production, it continuously and precisely measures all axis positions and temperatures, as well as material temperature and gas consumption.

It is also set up with a MQTT server with manufacturer-defined topics encompassing all aforementioned position, temperature and gas consumption data. Additionally it transmits status and further crucial process step data, thought to simplify correlation between measured data and planned program steps.

The tapes used for producing the preforms are usually commercial products supplied by different manufacturers all over the world. Therefore tapes as well as their raw materials like carbon fibers, matrices, precursors and other ingredients cannot be included explicitly into the in-house digitalized process chain. As a result, during LCA the environmental impact of tapes is computed using standardized data (e.g. datasheet or database values). However, in order to correlate information that is related to process quality, a custom built test bench is used to provide seamless quality information for every tape used in later processes [21]. The Tape-Quality-Bench (TQB) measures the precise cross section of the tested tape whilst also filming its surface using a polarization camera (VCXU-50MP, Baumer GmbH, Austria) for measuring fiber orientation close to the surface and check for defects and foreign objects.

4 CREATING THE INTERNAL SOLUTION: IIOT AND LIMS

Starting from the state as described before and an already in part created solution for a custom build Laboratory Information System (LIS), an example for the usage of a digital twin framework is created for the presented process. Here, internally developed software was combined with open-source code to create a solution that is able to be shared fully later on. The architecture and especially the workflow within this system is described to give a general overview about the internal use and capabilities and create a basis for the later following description of the externally shared AAS.

Data along the process chain is initially collected locally on the respective production machines—namely, the TQB, the F2-Compositor, and the Langzauner press—and subsequently transmitted to the internal Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) infrastructure. To accommodate the heterogeneous nature of legacy and modern machine controls, and their varying data export capabilities, the IIoT system exposes multiple data ingestion interfaces, including MQTT brokers, Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interfaces (RESTful APIs) and Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC UA) endpoints. This multi-protocol support ensures seamless integration of both current and future manufacturing assets. All incoming data to the IIoT system must be timestamped upon ingestion. Where timestamps are not natively provided by the machines, edge devices append them, synchronized via Network Time Protocol (NTP) servers. This ensures the temporal consistency of otherwise independent data sources, which enables automated detection of stale or delayed data, and facilitates precise correlation of process data streams.

In cases where not all relevant data is natively available from the machine control, the IIoT compensates by logically integrating supplementary data sources. For example, although the F2-Compositor does not report the energy consumption of its auxiliary aggregates, this gap is filled by an external energy monitoring device (Shelly Pro 3EM, Shelly Group SE, Bulgaria), which independently measures and transmits the data via MQTT. Its measurements are published under a structured topic hierarchy, e.g., `F2Compositor/Energy/Auxiliaries`, enabling semantic classification of the data stream. Through topic-based filtering and stream parsing, the IIoT system aggregates disparate signals into unified datasets associated with logical assets. This approach ensures semantic coherence even when physical data sources are decoupled. Temporal alignment is achieved via the shared timestamping infrastructure.

While the IIoT layer provides the backbone for scalable ingestion and storage of raw process data, including sensor values, machine parameters, and energy metrics, it does not itself impose any domain-specific structure. Semantic enrichment and high-level data modeling are instead delegated to the LIS. This architectural separation ensures modularity and scalability, with the IIoT handling efficient data logistics, and the LIS capturing contextual and semantic relationships. The LIS organizes data within a hierarchical structure conceptualized as a forest, where each tree corresponds to a specific project. Root nodes are labeled with unique project identifiers, which can optionally link to external project management systems. Subordinate nodes represent physical or logical entities (e.g., materials, processes, parts) and are enriched with attributes and metadata. Each node is uniquely identified via a Universally Unique Identifier (UUID). Nodes may be interlinked to express compositional, transformational, or inheritance-based relationships, thus capturing complex interdependencies within and between projects.

Figure 2: Representation of relationships between component instances along the manufacturing workflow in the internal solution

The manufacturing workflow, illustrated in Figure 2, begins with the thermoplastic tape, the smallest production unit. Bulk tape is initially registered in the LIS as a node containing general attributes such as type, manufacturer, mechanical properties, and nominal width as well as the PCF in form of a single numerical value. Individual spools derived from this bulk material are created as subordinate nodes. During initial quality assessment at the TQB, measured data is recorded and tagged with the associated spool's UUID, stored in the Influx time-series database of the IIoT system, resulting in a set of data which includes measured tape width and its cross-sectional height. At present, tape manufacturers do not provide machine-readable datasheets, digital product representations, or unique identifiers for individual spools. Consequently, UUIDs are generated internally by the LIS. These identifiers are physically linked to spools via QR codes, enabling consistent association between digital representations and physical items. Designed to digitally unify a set of discrete manufacturing processes

for fiber reinforced plastics, the system uses these QR codes to ensure end-to-end traceability. In addition, UUIDs serve as tags within the IIoT data streams, enabling seamless linkage between time-series data and LIS entities.

In the subsequent process step, spools are mounted on the F2-Compositor and identified via QR code scanning. This action associates the spool node with the current instance of the tape laying process and creates a new entity representing the manufactured preform. The resulting preform node automatically inherits attributes from the tape spool and is linked to process data that has been measured during its manufacturing by being linked to its parent node, which represents this manufacturing step. Users may augment these nodes with additional information such as program parameters, machine setup, manual observations, or process events, which are then available to downstream analyses. A persistent challenge in ATL processes is the correlation of process conditions with final part quality. While consolidation quality of the laminate has minimal impact, defects originating in the tape-laying step, such as wrinkled or flipped tows or foreign objects, can significantly impair quality. Although the F2-Compositor provides detailed process data, this alone has proven insufficient. Therefore, a laser line scanner (ScanCONTROL 3000-25/BL, Micro-Epsilon Messtechnik GmbH & Co. KG) is installed on the tape-laying head to capture the surface geometry of each layer. This sensor produces a continuous data stream, recorded as a time-series in the IIoT system and tagged to the corresponding laminate node in the LIS. This data can be evaluated either post-process or in real-time by subscribing to the F2-Compositor's MQTT data channels.

Finally, the laminate serves as the raw material in the thermoplastic stamp forming step. Each finished part is registered as a new node in the LIS, inheriting attributes from the laminate node and receiving its own UUID. Time-series data from this process is again captured in the Influx database. The exception is the thermal imaging data, acquired by an infrared camera. In contrast to the laser scanner, which generates continuous streams, the infrared system captures discrete images per part. These images are attached to the respective part node as singular or occasional multiple instances and are stored using MinIO (MinIO Inc., USA).

5 EXTERNAL SOLUTION: INTERFACING THROUGH AAS

The AAS is used to create external representations based on internally stored information. It is perfectly suited for this, because its modular and extensible structure allows for the integration of heterogeneously collected internal data, such as those originating from LIS, time-series databases or data processing and storage platforms, into a unified, semantically consistent model.

5.1 AAS Modeling using Standardized Submodels

AAS Structure and Infrastructure has a large degree of freedom in terms of information structure, especially in customized submodels. There are limitations of course, nesting of AAS and submodels is forbidden by the metamodel for example. In this way, the structure used in the internal implementation becomes impossible to reproduce. Instead, a new data model based on the AAS metamodel has to be created. Different implementations of the AAS can be used to achieve this easily, however there are no extensive and understandable guides for doing so yet. Also, for most cases there is currently no automated solution for checking the conformity to the metamodel or the used submodels.

In this way, defining the data structure is more difficult than it seems. Being compliant to other standards such as Concept Descriptions and SemanticIDs applies a large amount of implicit and explicit conventions, in addition to the constraints already applied by the metamodel. Handling this large amount of complexity correctly and creating fitting submodel structures is the most important aspect of the work, not only because it needs to be correct, but also because it needs to be widely applicable and understandable. In the following, an effort to structure the data created along the studied process chain is presented.

The starting point for defining the AAS from the finished part perspective is the relation between parts and resources. As stated before, nesting of AAS is not allowed. The alternative is to provide AAS with the information of either the parts containing them or alternatively the parts contained within. This is specified within the published submodel *IDTA 02011-1-1 Hierarchical Structures enabling Bills of Material*. Here, three model variants are allowed concerning the detail and way of relationship between

components. As thermoformed parts are not complete systems, the *full* type is not applicable, leaving the *one up* and *one down* modelling variants, where every component in an assembly hierarchy is linked to the ones it contains (*one down*) or the ones it is contained in (*one up*).

For our example, we define three types of AAS, representing different states of manufacturing. The first is the tapes and instances of it, being contained within preforms, which is in turn the currently single component of a thermoformed part. Whilst fitting to our internal model closely, as the parts are used up as resources they are not components that could be recovered from the thermoformed part. However, there is the benefit of being able to export any of those three steps as AAS without the need to create a model not considered in our structure, allowing for more flexible process routes as to export every step in between. The relation is created using the inherited parent node in the internal representation at the end of the parts manufacturing process tracked in the LIS. There, an associated AAS is derived from the node, already created with the corresponding submodel for the parent node, creating a submodel entry node as well as the node defining the relationship.

The now existing AAS instance is automatically created with two more submodels containing meta-information. The first one is the *IDTA 02002-1-0 Submodel for Contact Information*. This submodel describes IVW in the form of attributes as well as a contact person. Since the presented process chain is within IVW's manufacturing department, the contact information is per default the head of the manufacturing department. The submodel element collections within Contact Information also include additional data such as an email address and telephone and fax numbers as well as typically available times of day in relation to coordinated universal time.

Similarly, general information for *IDTA 02006-3-0 Digital Nameplate for Industrial Equipment* is set for the country of origin, company logo and production date as well as address information. Additionally, depending on the type of node, the product type is set as tape, preform or part as well. Furthermore, the link to the real part is stored here. The node's UUID reflecting the marking on the real part is set as serial number.

Each AAS created in this study also incorporates the *IDTA 02023 Carbon Footprint* submodel, enabling a structured and standardized assessment of greenhouse gas emissions throughout the production process. The carbon footprint represented by the submodel encapsulates the relevant data for PCF calculation. Within the *ProductCarbonFootprint* collection, the scope and the methodology for the assessment are defined. The Submodel Element List (SML) *LifeCyclePhases* specifies the considered life cycle stages according to the ECLASS 15 value list *LifeCyclePhase*. In this study, phase *A3 - production* is selected, corresponding to a gate-to-gate approach since the internal focus is placed on the production phase of each process. The SML *PcfCalculationMethods* contain the standards applied to the calculation. In this study, the internal calculation node is aligned with the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards with *Climate Change* as evaluated impact category. Quantitative results are stored as property *PcfCO2eq*, which holds the sum of greenhouse gas emissions as decimal in kilograms of CO₂-equivalent (kg CO₂-eq.). In this study, the reference unit of the product i.e. tapes, preforms, and thermoformed parts, is kilogram (kg). This layered and semantically enriched submodel structure supports transparent, traceable, and interoperable reporting of product carbon footprints.

Figure 3: Representation of submodels within the external AAS-based solution as an example for the preform as used in the process chain presented here

In the calculation of the PCF, a large amount of time series data is already used and does not need to be included in the AAS. Most other data acquired for process control purposes is also time series data. Whilst it is mostly used for internal purposes, the *IDTA 02008-1-1 Time Series Data* submodel is included as well to potentially share it externally. The submodel offers many different ways to add data to it and even manipulate the data within, if used as an active model. Since the purpose and way of using the process data is not fully defined for the example yet, the data is strictly passively attached as internal data segments. This means, the selected data is saved directly within the AAS. For the proposed processes, these are width and height of the tape instance, position of the ATL axis as well as forces applied in the thermoforming process.

As the data is already included within the internal nodes representing the corresponding process steps, the data just has to be exported to the AAS. This is also the step, where the control over process data export can be exercised. Because the data is already available as a link to influx database storage, every available data channel can be exported in the same way. Time series data corresponding to different measurement channels can be stored into individual segments of the time series submodel. The required timing information is taken directly from the Influx database in the form of Universal Coordinated Time (UTC) time stamps. Semantic data in the form of identifiers is taken from MQTT topics, including their respective data sources.

5.2 AAS Modelling of Composites and Composite Manufacturing

There are no implementations of composite-specific submodels or their processes yet. This means anybody is free to define data structures as preferred. This work uses Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) with the stacking rules for individual layers and mechanical characterization based on single layer-attributes as common ground. For this, a custom submodel *FlatFiberReinforcedLaminates*, as depicted in Figure 4 starts with the top level domain of macro-scale objects. Here, laminates and semi-finished laminates (preforms) are generally characterized as flat or deformed to conform to the needs of the thermoformed part. On the same level, the geometry of the full laminate is listed to describe strictly rectangular outlines in Cartesian notation. Here, actively calculated data for the laminates mechanical data based on the CLT calculations could be added in the future, generated from the single laminate layers. These are added as a submodel collection on this level of the model instead, integrating multiple layers as used in the stacking rules for laminate. Here, single layers are collected in a bottom to top order, named by their number of appearance within the laminate. Every single laminate is described by

their textile reinforcement structure, with lay-up as the only type used in this example. Additionally, the orientation angle of the layer is saved according to the rules of the laminate code as defined by NETTLES [22] and the height. Furthermore, the individual layers' mechanical attributes are added as an additional submodel. Here, the individual attributes as needed in the CLT are provided as properties. Further data such as areal weights and densities could be added, where available. Considering the use of thermoplastic matrices, an additional thermal submodel was set up to contain relevant thermal properties such as melting point and glass transition temperature. The original data sheet, where available is added to the layer model as well.

Figure 4: Depiction of an instance of a laminate shell within the AASX-Package Explorer

The presented model thus allows for the description of all states occurring within the demonstrated processing chain. Furthermore, the shared attributes between all states allows to copy or reference the submodel for process steps earlier in the process chain. In a possible next step, the matrices and fibers could be described as additional entities, resulting in a more detailed model.

6 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In the presented work, digital twins for a process chain based around thermoplastic stamp forming of tape layed preforms were created. The process is a promising combination of fast production and high performance products with less emissions during the production chain compared to thermosets. For aerospace applications the process chain needs improved process control and life cycle analysis, which can be easily achieved using Digital Twin. An internal twin to collect, aggregate and store the data has been created based on a custom solution. From it, an external twin has been derived which contains the same information but in a standardized exchangeable form, using the AAS. For this external representation, different aspects of structuring data have been presented and discussed. The most basic element of the taxonomy is the representation of the tape spool, which contains only generic data, such as the manufacturer or fiber type. On the next level, tapes are aggregated into laminate layers, which in turn are aggregated into laminates, following the rules of CLT. Finally, after the thermoforming process steps, these laminates are transformed into deformed parts by adding the deformed tag.

The presented model is but an example to create such a combination of digital twins along a process chain. Through the direct integration of PCF relevant measuring devices, the groundwork for LCA has been laid. Additional feedback opportunities for linking part quality and process quality have been integrated as well. Still, the digitalized process chain lacks some components, especially to reach the goal of proper lifecycle assessment, as well as integrations into ERP, MES or SCM systems. It can however, already show the advantages of digital twins alongside a process chain in creating a clearer data structure and effectively reducing individual management effort for process data. The investigation of part quality influences across multiple process steps with data science methods can only be realized in a manner where process data is collected and managed in an automatic way, enabling this promising field of work.

Altogether, the presented work cannot represent a fully defined standard, but using standardized elements from the AAS is already a large step into the direction of a digital twin. Information as contained in the submodel for carbon footprint will likely find their way in to the product passport and will thus be enforced for businesses. As it will be a requirement to provide similar structures in the near future, we recommended to start working with the subject as soon as a standard fit for long term use has been defined. In our opinion, the AAS could be just the one that prevails, and whilst the product carbon footprint may be obligatory, additional benefits from the use of process data can be generated.

By expanding our approach down to the fiber and matrix levels as well as the machines and finally to other processes for composite manufacturing such as filament winding or sheet molding compound, we can further enhance our understanding of relevant process parameters that can be shared in standardized models. This is especially important for using LCA as a predicting tool, e.g. for selecting suitable and sustainable production techniques in the future.

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